

Spectrophotometric Investigations on Chelate Formation in Cobalt (II)-2-Carboxyl 2'-Hydroxyl-3',5'-Dimethyl-Azobenzene-4-Sulphonic Acid (CHDMAS)-System

S. B. GHOLSE, A. S. GHORMADE and R. B. KHARAT*

Department of Chemistry, Nagpur University, Nagpur.

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CHDMAS^{1,2} has been recently synthesised in this laboratory and its interaction with Cu(II), Ni(II) and Pd(II) has been studied spectrophotometrically. Recently thermodynamic parameters of Fe(III)-CHDMAS system has been undertaken potentiometrically³. The present communication deals with the studies of conditional stability constant and analytical applications of the Co(II)-CHDMAS chelate.

Experimental

Spectrophotometric measurements were made on Beckman DU-2 spectrophotometer using silica cuvettes of 1 cm path length. All chemicals used were of A. R. grade.

The reagent CHDMAS was synthesised by method of Kharat & Sharma and its purity was checked by potentiometric titration, thin layer chromatography and by elemental analysis. Cobalt chloride solution was used. The pH of solutions were adjusted with NaOH and HCl. A green coloured water soluble complex was formed instantaneously and the colour intensity was found to be independent of the order of addition of reagents.

Results and Discussion

The pK₁ and pK₂ values of CHDMAS, determined spectrophotometrically are reported by Kharat and Sharma to be 3.54 and 10.8 respectively. However, under present experimental conditions the values of pK₁ and pK₂ have been found to be 3.55 and 10.8 respectively. Calvin and Bjerrum technique^{4,5} at an initial ionic strength of 0.04 has also been used to determine pK values, are 3.53 and 10.60 respectively. The -SO₃H group present might be dissociating at lower pH value and thus, not permitting its determination under the present conditions of study. The pK₂ value has been further refined by spectrophotometric method from the relation :

$$pK = pH + \log \frac{A_I - A}{A - A_M}$$

Where, A_I and A_M are the absorbances of the ion

and the molecule of the ligand and A that of a series of mixtures of ions and molecules. This gave a value of 10.85 for pK₂.

Absorption spectra of the ligand shows the shifts in λ_{max} with pH. From pH 1.0 to 10.0 the λ_{max} was at 340 nm. However, two λ_{max} were observed at 340 and 490 nm in the pH range 11.0 to 12.0.

Vosburgh and Cooper's method⁶ showed the existence of one complex giving the maxima 630 nm at pH 7.5. No effect of temperature (25°-90°) was observed on the absorbance values (by keeping the volume constant). The chelate was stable for more than 120 hr. and in the pH range 7.0-10.0 (when the ratio of the metal : ligand was 1:4).

The composition of the chelate was established to be 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) by the method of continuous variations⁷, mole ratio method⁸, and slope ratio method⁹. Conditional stability constant was calculated using Dey and coworkers method¹⁰⁻¹² and the average value of log K was found to be 7.5±0.3.

Analytical applications : Six fold excess of reagent was required for maximum colour intensity. The absorbance of the complex was measured at 630 nm against reagent blank. Beer's law holds good in the range 0.58-2.35 ppm and the effective photometric range was found to be 1.1-1.5 ppm. of Co(II). The average molar absorptivity at pH 7.5 and at λ_{max} 630 nm is 4.0625×10³ with Sandell's sensitivity 0.053 μg/cm². The average and relative standard deviation were 0.001 and 1.25 percent respectively.

The ions which do not interfere at all concentrations are Cl⁻, Br⁻, I⁻, CH₃COO⁻, S₂O₃²⁻, Ag⁺, Ga³⁺, In³⁺ and Al³⁺. The ions which seriously interfere are Mn²⁺, Zn²⁺, C₂O₄²⁻, C₄H₄O₆²⁻, C₆H₅O₇³⁻ and EDTA⁴⁻ (±5% deviation in absorbance value was arbitrarily taken as interference).

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References

- O. P. SHARMA and R. B. KHARAT, *Indian J. Chem.* 1975, 13, 848.
- O. P. SHARMA, Ph.D. thesis submitted to Nagpur University, Nagpur, 1975.
- B. K. DESHMUKH, ALKA BOKARE and R. B. KHARAT, *Indian J. Chem.* 1976, 14A, 541.
- M. CALVIN and K. W. WILSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 2003.
- J. BJERRUM, "Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solution". Hasse, Copenhagen, 1941, p. 298.
- W. C. VOSBURGH and G. R. COOPER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 437.
- P. JOB, *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, 9, 113.
- J. H. YOE and A. L. JONES, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1944, 16, 111.
- A. E. HARVEY and D. L. MANNING, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 4488.
- A. K. DEY, *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1948, 3, 473.
- A. K. DEY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 25, 571.
- A. K. DEY, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. (India)*, 1949, 18A, 121; 1950, 19A, 148; *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1964, 37, 1875.